

Microstructure (Microtexture), Structure and Surface Studies of Some Carbon Fibres

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ABSTRACT

Nine high modulus PAN-base fibres and six high tensile strength PAN-base fibres were studied. Their microtexture and their structure were determined by conventional transmission electron microscopy. Their mechanical properties were then determined. The microtexture of high modulus fibres is made of relatively large sheets of aromatic layers, distorted and intermingled with an apparent skin and core effect. High tensile strength fibres are homogeneous and made of basic structural units less than 10 Å in size the arrangement of which is similar to the high modulus model. Only the transverse radius of curvature changes from one type of fibre to the other ones.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical properties of carbon fibre-glassy polymer composites depend partly on the fibre properties and partly on adhesion. The fibre properties themselves are connected to their microstructure and structure whereas adhesion is related to the interface between the polymer and the fibre surface. High resolution conventional transmission electron microscope (CTEM) was used for studying various kinds of fibres. Thin-sectioning was carried out either transversally or longitudinally by using an ultra-microtome equipped with a diamond knife. CTEM techniques were mainly selected area electron diffraction (SAD), 002 lattice fringes and tilted dark-field exploration of the whole available reciprocal space.

PAN-fibres, either high modulus (Celion GY 70, Courtaulds HMS E2M 278D (82), Serofim AG 25,58,0413.11,4212.1;AGT 4022.6, 4033.3 and 4022.4) or high tensile strength ones (Toray 300 40B 1600501, 90A 0140562, Courtaulds XAS6KILXA 102 B 2A, Serofim AXT 4626.15, 3245.EY, Celanese 1000 HTA 8W 7511) were observed. Longitudinal and transverse thin sections lead first to determine the crystalline order of the fibres, then to determine their microtexture. The microtexture of most of the high modulus fibres obeys a unique model made of more or less distorted aromatic layer stacks having a variable transverse radius of curvature ρ_T which decreases continuously from the surface to the centre, giving an appearance of skin and core. On the contrary, the Courtaulds HMS fibre may obey the Johnson model. This latter is made of closely entangled distorted carbon layers without skin and core effect. The radius of curvature is largely smaller than that of the preceding ones.

All the high tensile strength fibres have a very small ρ_T relative to the high modulus ones. However, they can be classified by decreasing values of a compactness index of the aromatic layers. Most of the high tensile strength fibres studied are inhomogeneous both from one set to another and from one single fibre to the adjacent one and also from one region to another in the same fibre (particularly Celanese 1000 HTA and Toray 300 40B).

The mechanical properties were found to be directly correlated to the compactness index Δ_T .

RESULTS

High Modulus Fibres

Fig. 1. SAD pattern of a fibre.

Lamellar Model, The model represented in figure 2 is the one which fits best with the bright and dark field images of all the fibres except Courtaulds HMS. This model is made of large sheets of carbon layer stacks crumpled, distorted and intermingled (1,2,3). An individual stack (basic structural unit or BSU) is sketched in figure 3. Its diameter is L_a , its thickness L_c and its transverse radius of curvature ρ_T . The profiles of such BSU are represented in figures 4a, 5a and 6a. Their radius of curvature decreases from 4a to 6a, which indicates a fold more and more developed. Such figures are used (4) to predict all the possible electron microscope images which can be obtained after longitudinal sectioning.

In bright field mode, the objective aperture is set in position 1 of figure 1. In 002 dark field mode, it is set in position 2 and in position 3 and 4 respectively in 10 and 11 dark

SAD Patterns, The SAD pattern is sketched in figure 1. It is similar in all the fibres which are mostly turbostratic, i.e., which show carbon layers piled-up in complete azimuthal disorder. At the most, the fibre surface can be partially graphitized but only a very few pairs of carbon layers have reached the graphite order.

Fig. 2. Model of a fibre.

Fig. 3. Schematic drawing of a basic structural unit.

Figs. 4, 5 and 6. From 4 to 6, the radius of curvature decreases.
 a) Transverse section of a basic structural unit.
 b), c) and d) Schematic drawings of bright and dark field micrographs :
 b) bright field and 002 dark field images,
 c) 10 dark field images,
 d) 11 dark field images.

field mode. In figure 4b, no contrast is visible neither in bright field nor in 002 dark field since the aromatic layers never reach the 002 Bragg angle. In 10 and 11 dark field mode, rotational moiré fringes appear respectively perpendicular to the fibre axis (Fig. 4c) and parallel to it (Fig. 4d). In 10 dark field images, since the size of the aperture is finite (Fig. 1), the aromatic layers cannot be tilted more than a defined value for the moiré fringes to be visible (this angle is 34° for a 0.2 \AA^{-1} aperture). Their length is thus limited to $2 \rho_T \sin 34^\circ$. The bright scattering regions are ribbon-like with a length L_a . However, in 11 dark field, the BSU always yield 11 scattering. As ρ_T decreases (Fig. 5), areas such as m or n reach the 002 Bragg angle. Dark 002 bands become visible in dark field images whereas bright 002 bands appear in 002 dark field ones (Fig. 5b). In the same way, 004 bright bands appear in 10 dark field mode since the 004 reflection is very close to 10 and thus passes through the aperture opening (Fig. 5c). In 11 dark field mode, the moiré fringes are seen progressively more obliquely close to m and n areas. Becoming closer to one another, they tend to superimpose. When the aromatic layers fulfill exactly the 002 Bragg condition, the moiré fringes disappear. In the m or n areas of the 11 dark field images, characteristic pairs of diffuse bright lines appear separated by a dark band (Fig. 5d). In figure 6 b and c, ρ_T decreases again. However, the 002 and 10 dark field images are like figure 5 ones whereas the m and n 002 and 004 bands are closer. More striking differences are observed in 11 dark field mode (Fig. 6d). Since the areas which separate two successive m or n zones get progressively smaller, the moiré fringes tend to blur and even to disappear. Only the pairs of diffuse bright lines which appear along the rim of m and n areas remain clearly visible.

Table 1

Sample	Size	L_a (Å)	L_c (Å)	ρ_T (Å)	E (G.Pa)	σ (G.Pa)
Serofim AG 25 } Serofim AG 58 }	no	800-1000 (skin)	60-100	skin \approx 200 core $>$ 100	420	1.52
Celion GY 70	yes	500-700	60	skin \approx 250 core $>$ 60	430	1.53
Serofim AG 0413.11	no	200-400	50	skin \approx 80 core \geq 30	323	2.19
Serofim AGT 4022.6	yes	200-300	50	-	304	1.67
Serofim AGT 4033.3	yes	200-300	50	-	365*	2.01*
Serofim AGT 4022.4	no	200-300	50	-	320	2.14
Serofim AG 4212.1	no	200-300	50	-	326	2.41
Courtaulds HMS E2M 278 D(82)	yes	300-600	50	-	361	2.41

* Commercial values.

L_a , L_c and ρ_T can be deduced from the various images from figure 4 to figure 6. ρ_T can be obtained from the 002 lattice images given by transverse sections. In longitudinal thin sections and in transverse one as well, the 002 fringes appear straight and perfect and the aromatic layers also are thus stiff and perfect. From these results, it can be concluded that the high modulus fibres here observed were heat-treated above 2000°C (5,6). All of them show a decrease of ρ_T from the surface to the core. Nevertheless this decrease is progressive and the pores are flattened also close to the surface. This causes an apparent skin and core effect when the fibres are observed in optical microscopy. The various fibres are classified in table 1 by decreasing ρ_T . The same table also presents the values of L_a and L_c , the Young modulus and the tensile strength σ .

Other Model, It has to be noted that the Courtaulds HMS fibre (Table 1) could be different from the other ones. Its transverse radius of curvature is so small that it cannot be evaluated. Longitudinal sections, when observed in phase contrast electron microscopy (002 lattice fringes) suggest interpenetration of the layers. This interpenetration seems to be added to the intermingling of the layers (7). Such a fibre could obey the model of Johnson *et al.* (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Model of a fibre from (7).

High Tensile Strength Fibres

The samples here studied are Toray 300 40B 1600501, 90A 0140562, Courtaulds XAS 6 KILXA 102B2A, Serofim AXT 4626.15, 3245.EY, Celanese 1000 HTA 8W.7511. Their basic structural units are less than 10 Å, i.e. they are not much different in diameter from polyaromatic molecules such as coronene for instance. All of them are turbostratic. They show local rearrangements approximately parallel with tilt and twist boundaries. They form large wrinkled layers. Most of these fibres are inhomogeneous and this heterogeneity is indicated in table 2.

Table 2

Sample	Size	Inhomogeneity	E_d (G.Pa)	E_s (G.Pa)	σ (G.Pa)	Δ_T
Toray 300 40B 1600501	yes	yes	209	225	3	0.9
Toray 300 90A 0140562	no	yes	-	226*	3.04*	0.9
Courtaulds XAS 6 KILXA 102B2A	no	yes	223	243	2.75	0.8
Serofim AXT 4626.15	no	yes	182	209	2.31	0.6
Celanese 1000 HTA 8W 7511	yes	yes	209	229	1.93	0.5
Serofim AXT 3245.EY	yes	no	191	213	1.86	0.3

* Commercial values. E_d initial modulus, E_s mean modulus.

In such disordered systems, ρ_T can be no more defined since it can vary from one set of adjacent BSU to the next one. The fibres are classified in table 2 by using a compactness index Δ_T deduced from the 002 lattice fringe images. In high modulus fibres, the thickness L_C (i.e. the number N of parallel layers) has a constant value and the layers piled up cannot be separated from one another. The pores have thus walls of equal thickness with a unique value of ρ_T . In high tensile strength fibres, the BSU are only molecules either single or piled up by 2 or 3 (at the most). The wrinkled layers thus formed can be distorted transversally in the material independently from one another (ρ_T cannot be defined any longer).

From place to place, they can be found either alone or gathered in parallel by 2, 3 or more. Their relative position varies at random all over the material. The resulting texture is opened increasingly as the compactness of the wrinkled layers decreases. The compactness index Δ_T is maximum when many layers are piled up together and remain associated in the same way everywhere in the material. In this case, either Δ_T or ρ_T can be used as a criterion (see Toray 300 40B, for instance). On the contrary, if each wrinkled layer is distorted alone or only by 2 or 3, Δ_T is minimum (Serofim 3245, for instance).

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The mechanical properties of high modulus single filaments were carried out by means of a microtensile machine especially designed for carbon fibres. A commercial Adamel-Lomargy tensile machine was used for high strength carbon fibres. In the first case, the gauge length was about 15 mm, in the second one, 100 mm. Monofilament tests are long to perform. So two different machines were used, the former one for HM fibres, the latter one for HS fibres. In our case, strength values depend on the gauge length. They are not intrinsic but the strengths of various fibres of same gauge length can be compared. Cross section of each fibre was determined by MEB with well calibrated magnification in order to obtain values of Young's modulus and strength. HM fibres have a Hookean behaviour. In the case of HS fibres, a strengthening of the material with increasing load was observed possibly due to stress-induced reorientation of high turbostratic aromatic planes. Young's modulus increases about 15 % between loading and failure. Table 2 contains initial and mean values of HS fibres modulus.

CONCLUSION

Carbon fibre structure and microtexture were found to be correlated with some mechanical parameters. A relationship was found to exist between the fibre Young's modulus and the structure parameter L_a which is a measure of the average distance between layer-plane imperfections in high modulus fibres. Significant correlations were found between the tensile strength σ and the fibre curvature radius ρ_T for high modulus fibres and the compactness index Δ_T for high tensile strength fibres.

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